

A Study On Mediation Effect Of Social Media Satisfaction To Get Brand Loyalty From Hedonic And Utilitarian Shopping Value

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Abstract

*Purpose:*This research paper analyses mediation effect of Social Media satisfaction to get Brand Loyalty from Hedonic and Utilitarian Shopping value. Since every customer looks for Hedonic and Utilitarian Shopping value before buying any product. If he consistently gets the value from the product over a period of time, he develops satisfaction which eventually leads to Brand loyalty. This study intends to find out whether Hedonic and Utilitarian Shopping value needs some level of Social Media satisfaction to achieve Brand Loyalty. *Methodology/Approach:*A quantitative based approach method is used by examining various primary and secondary sources of information and doing a systematic analysis of observed data. Using SPSS-AMOS software a model was developed to study the mediation effect of Social Media satisfaction to get Brand Loyalty from Hedonic and Utilitarian Shopping value. *Findings:* it was found that there is mediation effect of Social Media satisfaction on Brand Loyalty. If we try to remove the mediation variable Social Media Satisfaction from the model and try to study the effect of Hedonic and Utilitarian Shopping value on brand loyalty then it was found that the model didn't give desired results. *Research limitations/future scope:*There are many studies on impact of social media on brand image done internationally, but not much work has been done on Indian companies. In this research we made an effort to study how social media has helped Indian companies to enhance their brand image and to reach out in a better way to their customers. *Practical implications:*The findings from this study will be useful in application of theory; more specifically the application of social penetration theory and social exchange theory on the effect of social media use on building brand equity will be appreciated. *Further, the academicians and business researchers will borrow from the findings of this research to support literary citations as well as develop themes for further research. The Originality/value of paper:*The academicians and business researchers will borrow from the findings of this research to support literary citations as well as develop themes for further research.

Introduction

Social media locales and the buildup around this sort of media are empowered by the specialized basis of Web 2.0, which given the plausibility for web clients to make them possess substance (too called User-Generated Substance). A social media side can be characterized as an intelligently site giving data, whereas at the same time the substance can be some way or another impacted. This prepare can be decently straightforward by inquiring for a person's supposition or a rating, or maybe complex. There are many studies on impact of social media on brand image done internationally, but not much work has been done on Indian companies. In this research we made an effort to study how social media has helped Indian companies to enhance their brand image and to reach out in a better way to their customers. The research of online consumer behavior has been widely conducted in both information systems and marketing science fields. However, most of the studies have been published in information systems literature, implying that most e-commerce studies have been done in the information systems world. Koufaris (2002) gave an explanation on this, that is, it is perhaps more accurate to view e-commerce as an information systems phenomenon where user of information systems interacts with a complex information system, rather than viewing e-commerce as a marketing issue influenced by information systems' usage. The similar argument has also been given by other scholars. Although traditional consumer behavior is well described by marketing and economic theories, overwhelming evidence suggests that information systems-related variables have become at least as important as traditional factors in predicting consumer behavior on the Internet.

Research methodology:

The universe of this study consists of the adults which include students, salaried, self-employed and housewives.

Sample Size:

Zone	Students	Salaried	Self employed	Housewife	Total
North	25	25	25	25	100
South	25	25	25	25	100
East	25	25	25	25	100
West	25	25	25	25	100
Central	25	25	25	25	100
Grand Total	125	125	125	125	500

Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability Estimates: A pilot study carried out over a period of one month has revealed that survey instrument is stable considering the new area of study. Bagozzi (1980) and Bagozzi and Philips (1991) recommend methods to ensure reliability and validity of measuring instrument itself. Initial data collection follows normal distribution based on skewness and kurtosis limits. Discriminant validity and composite reliability is found acceptable as per published guidelines (Fornell and Larckne, 1981) and these are as follows:

- Hedonic Shopping Value – Discriminant Validity 0.461 and Composite Reliability > 0.7 and found “Acceptable”
- Utilitarian Shopping Value - Discriminant Validity 0.466 and Composite Reliability > 0.7 and found “Acceptable”
- Social Media Satisfaction - Discriminant Validity 0.534 and Composite Reliability > 0.7 and found “Acceptable”
- Brand Loyalty - Discriminant Validity 0.454 and Composite Reliability > 0.7 and found “Acceptable”

Test of hypothesis:

H_N: There is no impact of Hedonic Shopping value and utilitarian Shopping value on Brand Loyalty is mediated by Social Media Satisfaction.

H_A: The Impact of Hedonic Shopping value and utilitarian Shopping value on Brand Loyalty is mediated by Social Media Satisfaction.

The hypothesis was tested using SPSS-AMOS model.

Below are Cronbach alpha values obtained from survey questionnaire testing with small sample.

- Hedonic Shopping Value - 0.690, described as “satisfactory”
- Utilitarian Shopping Value - 0.703, described as “good”
- Social Media Satisfaction - 0.780, described as “good”
- Brand Loyalty - 0.697, described as “satisfactory”

Variables: There are two independent variables Hedonic Shopping value and Utilitarian Shopping Value and Dependent value is Brand Loyalty and Social Media Satisfaction is mediating variable

The independent variables are:**Hedonic Shopping Value:**

This variable includes following factors:

Online shopping is always exciting for me, online shopping gives me more pleasure than what I get from the products purchased, compared to other things I could do, the time spent online shopping is/are truly enjoyable, I continue to shop not because I have to, but because I want to

Utilitarian value:

This variable includes following factors:

The products and services I purchase online are always right priced and are of good quality, I am successful in my online shopping, while shopping online, I search just the items I am looking for, I am able to buy what I really need, I am able to accomplish just what I want on the online shopping trip

Dependent variable:**Brand Loyalty**

This variable includes following factors:

I will continue to be a follower of this brand, I express positive things about this brand to other people, I recommend this brand to someone who seeks my advice, I intend to recommend this brand to other people

Mediating Variable:

Social Media Satisfaction

This variable includes following factors:

I am very satisfied with the service provided by (service), This (service) does a good job of satisfying my needs, the service provided by (service) is very satisfactory, I believe that using this service is usually a very satisfying experience, I believe that using this service is usually a very satisfying experience

AMOS model developed by Researcher:

HSV- Hedonic Shopping value, USV – Utilitarian Shopping value, SMS – Social Media Satisfaction and BL- Brand Loyalty

The proposed model was tested in AMOS software and the values of the variables for Absolute fit Model are as follows:

Model Fit Indices	Recommended Values	Observed Value	Authors
Chi-square (CMIN/DF)	1-5	1.9	Bollen and Long (1993) and Kelloway (1995)
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	> 0.90	0.916	Byrne, 1994
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	> 0.90	0.949	Bollen, 1990
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	> 0.90	1.003	Bollen, 1990
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	> 0.90	1.011	Hu and Bentler, 1998
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.90	1	Byrne, 1994
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	< 0.08	0.000	Browne and Sugawara, 1996

There is mediating effect of the variable social media satisfaction since after removing it from the above model we are not getting model fit values. Hence, we can reject null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis states that there is impact of Hedonic Shopping value and utilitarian Shopping value on Brand Loyalty is mediated by Social Media Satisfaction.

Findings and Conclusions:

- There is impact of Hedonic Shopping value and utilitarian Shopping value on Brand Loyalty is mediated by Social Media Satisfaction.
- Without social media satisfaction we cannot get brand loyalty.
- Hedonic shopping value and utilitarian shopping value do not directly lead to brand shopping.
- Hedonic Shopping value has direct positive impact on Social Media Satisfaction.
- Utilitarian value has direct positive impact on Social Media Satisfaction.
- Social Media Satisfaction has direct positive impact on Brand Loyalty.

Future scope:

- Further, the academicians and business researchers will borrow from the findings of this research to support literary citations as well as develop themes for further research.
- This study is also significant to the several sectors like hospitality industry, etc. It will help to determine the most popular types of social media sites used by hospitality industry and other sectors and effect of social media on building brand equity.
- Policy makers, such as the Ministry of Tourism, etc will gain insights on how to capitalize on social media platforms for promoting and reviving tourism, etc. Also, the regulators can appreciate the cyber security issues faced by organizations that have adopted social media, as part of their business operations.

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